

SERUM CALCIUM AND MAGNESIUM DYSREGULATION IN TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS: ASSOCIATIONS WITH GLYCEMIC CONTROL AND DISEASE COMPLICATIONS

¹Teslim Olalekan Adebayo, ¹Ismail Olaitan Adeyanju, ¹Abdulramon Opeyemi Muraina, ¹Maryam Adeyinka Ibraheem, ¹Halimah Olabisi Giwa, ²Adekunle Abiodun Adesiyun and ³Abdullahi Olaleye Olawuyi

Article Info

Keywords: serum magnesium, serum calcium, glycemic control, HbA1c, fasting blood glucose.

DOI

10.5281/zenodo.20023842

Abstract

Background: Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a chronic metabolic disorder characterised by insulin resistance and impaired insulin secretion, with an increasing global prevalence and significant public health implications. Alterations in serum calcium and magnesium have been linked to poor glycemic control and diabetes-related complications, yet these parameters are often neglected in routine management. **Objective:** This study aimed to evaluate serum calcium and magnesium levels in individuals with T2DM and determine their association with glycemic control and complications. The objectives were to assess the prevalence of calcium and magnesium abnormalities in patients with T2DM, examine correlations between these electrolytes and glycemic markers (HbA1c and fasting blood glucose), and explore associations with diabetic complications, including neuropathy, nephropathy, and retinopathy. **Methods:** A cross-sectional study involving 80 participants (50 T2DM patients and 30 healthy controls) was conducted in Osun State, Nigeria. The data collection methods included structured questionnaires, anthropometric measurements, and biochemical analyses of FBG, HbA1c, serum calcium, and magnesium. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 26, employing descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and t-tests, with $p < 0.05$ considered significant. **Results:** Showed that diabetic participants were significantly older, with serum magnesium levels markedly lower in

¹Department of Medical Laboratory Science, Fountain University, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria

²Department of Medical Laboratory Science, Osun State University, Osogbo, Osun State, Nigeria

³Department of Medical Laboratory Science, Federal University of Health Sciences, Ila-Orangun, Osun State, Nigeria

people with diabetes (1.47 ± 0.34 mmol/L) compared to controls (1.89 ± 0.18 mmol/L, $p < 0.05$), while serum calcium showed no significant difference. Magnesium exhibited a moderate negative correlation with FBG ($r = -0.559$, $p < 0.001$) and HbA1c ($r = -0.622$, $p < 0.001$), whereas calcium showed no significant correlation with either. **Conclusion:** Magnesium deficiency was common and strongly associated with poor glycemic control, suggesting it may serve as a biochemical indicator in T2DM. Therefore, it can be concluded that magnesium assessment should be incorporated into diabetes care protocols, alongside conventional glycemic markers. Recommendations include patient education on magnesium-rich diets, consideration of supplementation under medical guidance, and larger longitudinal studies to confirm causal relationships and evaluate the benefits of magnesium correction on long-term outcomes.

Introduction

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a chronic metabolic disease that produces elevated blood sugar due to insulin resistance and reduced insulin availability (Galicia-García et al., 2020). The condition is a major global public health issue because diagnostic rates are rapidly increasing worldwide, including both developed and developing countries (Hossain et al., 2024).

Type 2 diabetes mellitus produces long-term complications that result in cardiovascular issues, kidney damage, and nerve deterioration, as well as eye complications known as retinopathy, which cause major morbidity and numerous deaths annually (Deol & Bashir, 2024).

Many physiological processes depend on essential micronutrients such as calcium and magnesium, which assist enzymes, activate neuromuscular activity, and regulate glucose metabolism (Gröber, 2023). The cofactor role of magnesium enables many enzymes in carbohydrate metabolism and controls both insulin production and cellular response to insulin (Dastgerdi et al., 2022). The intracellular insulin-mediated metabolic processes that occur in insulin-responsive tissues, including skeletal muscle and adipose tissue, require calcium as a vital element (Contreras-Ferrat et al., 2014).

Studies have found that T2DM patients exhibit changes in serum calcium and magnesium levels, which affect diabetic control and increase the risk of diabetic complications, according to Pham (2007) and Rodriguez-Moran & Guerrero-Romero (2014). The condition hypomagnesemia affects many T2DM patients, leading to adverse consequences for both glycemic control and insulin resistance and disease complication risk (Hamarshih et al., 2022).

Insulin secretion and insulin resistance worsen when patients with diabetes exhibit problems with calcium homeostasis (Ahn et al., 2018).

New approaches to managing diabetes complications might be derived from studies of the relationships between serum calcium and magnesium concentrations and glucose levels in T2DM patients (Kocyigit et al., 2023). Evaluating trace elements in diabetic patients provides clinicians with important clinical information, as these elements are affected by diet, disease processes, and medications (Sanjeevi et al., 2018).

90–95% of diabetes cases belong to Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM), which develops because of genetic and environmental effects, as well as behavioural modifications (WHO, 2021). Studies show that diabetes affected

537 million adults worldwide in 2021, while researchers project this number to reach 643 million by 2030, according to the International Diabetes Federation (2021). The diabetes epidemic continues to increase in sub-Saharan Africa alongside other developing countries because of shifting lifestyles and ageing populations with urban populations (Ojuka & Goyaram, 2014).

Diabetic outcomes worsen because T2DM patients frequently develop electrolyte problems, especially when calcium and magnesium levels are unbalanced (Kocyigit et al., 2023). The transport of glucose across cell membranes and the regulation of insulin receptor activity depend on magnesium as a crucial element (Kostov, 2019). Pancreatic beta-cells use calcium for insulin secretion because this ion also regulates multiple cellular signalling events (Weiser et al., 2021).

T2DM patients exhibit lower serum magnesium concentrations due to urinary magnesium loss, inadequate dietary intake, and impaired absorption arising from hyperglycemia (Kuppusamy et al., 2022). Studies show that insulin resistance, together with diabetic inflammatory processes, is associated with changes in calcium metabolism that affect both serum levels and tissue distribution.

The vital nature of the connection among diabetes complications, glycemic control, and serum calcium and magnesium levels requires evaluation to develop better preventive care strategies.

Present-day clinical practice overlooks serum magnesium and calcium assessments in T2DM patients when performing routine blood analysis that mainly focuses on blood glucose, HbA1c, and lipid profiles (Kocyigit et al., 2023). The omission of serum magnesium and calcium evaluation results in unidentified deficiencies that affect insulin signalling and glycemic control, thus raising the possibility of complications (Divya et al., 2021).

The relationship between blood magnesium and calcium levels and HbA1c values appears inconsistent based on findings from Chakraborty et al. (2021) and Islam et al. (2018), as these results are affected by confounding variables, small sample sizes, and population-specific characteristics. Local research focused on nutritional deficiencies and healthcare limitations should take precedence because this area lacks context-specific investigations.

The prevention or delay of diabetic complications such as neuropathy and nephropathy can be achieved through early detection of micronutrient imbalances (Gautam et al., 2024). The failure to fully evaluate various factors will limit healthcare professionals' ability to implement well-rounded management strategies for T2DM patients.

This study, therefore, aimed to:

1. Determine the serum calcium and magnesium abnormalities in T2DM patients.
2. Assess the correlation between serum calcium and magnesium levels and glycemic control as measured by HbA1c.
3. Examine the relationship between serum calcium and magnesium dysregulation and the presence of diabetes complications such as nephropathy, retinopathy, and neuropathy.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

To evaluate the serum calcium and magnesium levels in individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus and their association with glycemic control and diabetes-related complications.

Methodology

Study Design

A cross-sectional study design was employed to evaluate the relationship between serum calcium and magnesium levels and glycemic control in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM). The cross-sectional approach was appropriate because it allowed for the simultaneous assessment of biochemical and clinical parameters within a defined population at a specific point in time, providing insights into correlations between electrolytes and glycemic indices (Adeyosola et al., 2021).

Study Area

The study was conducted at Uniosun Teaching Hospital in Oshogbo, which is the capital of Osun State in southwestern Nigeria. The Osun State region is located on a latitude of approximately 7 ° 30 'N and 4 ° 30'E, and Osogbo (the location of the study) is at latitude 7.78 ° N, longitude 4.54 ° E (= 7 ° 46 'N, 4 ° 33'E).

Osogbo is the administrative and commercial capital of the state and has some of the state's major health facilities, including diabetes care facilities; hence, a feasible location to recruit Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus patients from both the urban and directly adjacent rural populations. (Adeyosola et al., 2021)

Target Population

The study population comprised adult patients (≥ 30 years) with a confirmed diagnosis of T2DM attending the outpatient department at UNIOSUN Teaching Hospital in Osun State. Eligibility criteria required patients to be on active management for at least six months. Exclusion criteria included individuals with known chronic kidney disease, liver disorders, or those receiving calcium or magnesium supplementation, since such conditions could significantly influence serum electrolyte levels. Apparently healthy adults from the same community without a history of diabetes or chronic illness were recruited as controls.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria:

- Confirmed Diagnosis of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus
- Adult Patients
- Patients not currently experiencing acute diabetic emergencies, such as: Diabetic ketoacidosis and Hyperosmolar hyperglycemic state

Exclusion criteria:

- Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD)
- Current Use of Certain Medications

Patients currently using Calcium supplements, Magnesium supplements, Vitamin D supplements, Long-term corticosteroids, Pregnancy and Lactation, Pregnant women and Breastfeeding mothers.

Sample Size Determination

The sample size was determined using Cochran's formula for cross-sectional studies:

Based on this calculation, a minimum of 80 participants was determined to be adequate to achieve statistical significance. This comprised 50 confirmed T2DM patients (test group) and 30 apparently healthy individuals (control group).

Data Collection Procedures

A structured questionnaire adapted from validated diabetes research tools in sub-Saharan Africa was used to collect demographic information (age, sex, and occupation), lifestyle factors (diet, alcohol, and smoking), medical history, and duration of diabetes. Clinical assessments included measurement of blood pressure using a digital sphygmomanometer.

Weight and height were measured using standardised protocols. Body mass index (BMI) was calculated as weight (kg)/height² (m²).

Fasting Blood Glucose (FBG):

- Measured using the Glucose Oxidase–Peroxidase (GOD-POD) method. Plasma glucose is oxidised by glucose oxidase to produce gluconic acid and hydrogen peroxide, which reacts with chromogen in the presence of peroxidase to form a colored compound measured at 505 nm (Guerrero-Romero & Rodríguez-Morán, 2002; Bhatt et al., 2021).

Glycated Haemoglobin (HbA1c):

- It is assessed using a fluorescence immunoassay method. Fluorescently labelled antibodies bind to HbA1c, and an analyser quantifies the emitted signal. Results reflect mean plasma glucose over the previous 2–3 months (Suliman, 2021; Dastgerdi et al., 2022).

Serum Calcium:

- It is estimated using the Arsenazo III colourimetric method. Calcium ions in the sample react with the Arsenazo III dye in an acidic medium to form a blue-purple complex, whose intensity is directly proportional to the calcium concentration and can be measured spectrophotometrically at 650 nm (Yadav et al., 2020; Hashim et al., 2022; Kocuyigit et al., 2023). Reference range: 8.1–10.4 mg/dL (Itam et al., 2022).

Serum Magnesium:

- It is measured using the Xylidyl Blue colourimetric method. Magnesium reacts with Xylidyl Blue in an alkaline medium to form a red complex, which is measured spectrophotometrically at 520 nm. EGTA was included in the reagent to prevent calcium interference (Bass et al., 2016; Gröber, 2023; Kebir & Zahzeh, 2022). Reference range: 1.7–2.5 mg/dL (Hamarshih et al., 2022; Kuppusamy et al., 2022).

All blood samples were collected after 8–10 hours of overnight fasting. Venous blood was obtained under aseptic conditions, centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes, and serum aliquots were stored at –20°C until analysis.

Variables

- **Independent variables:** Serum calcium and serum magnesium concentrations.
- **Dependent variables:** Glycemic control indicators (HbA1c, FBG) and presence of complications.
- **Confounding variables:** Age, sex, BMI, comorbidities, and medication use.

Data Analysis

Data were analysed using SPSS version 26. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, frequencies) summarised participant characteristics. Independent-samples t-tests compared biochemical parameters between the diabetic and control groups. Pearson’s correlation was used to assess associations between serum electrolytes and glycemic indices. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Osun State Ministry of Health Research Ethics Committee. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants after the study objectives, procedures, risks, and benefits were explained. Confidentiality was maintained through anonymised data coding, and participants were informed of their right to withdraw at any stage without consequences.

Results

Table 1: Age Group Distribution for Diabetic (n=50) and control group (n=30)

Age Group	Test (n=50) Frequency	Test (%)	Control (n=30) Frequency	Control (%)	Total (n=80) Frequency	Total (%)
<40	4	8.0	19	63.3	23	28.7
40–49	16	32.0	5	16.7	21	26.2
50–59	15	30.0	1	3.3	16	20.0
60–69	15	30.0	4	13.3	19	23.8
70+	0	0.0	1	3.3	1	1.2
Total	50	100.0	30	100.0	80	100.0

Table 2: Gender Group Distribution of Diabetic (n=50) and Control Group (n=30)

Gender	Test (n=50) Frequency	Test (%)	Control (n=30) Frequency	Control (%)	Total (n=80) Frequency	Total (%)
F	26	52.0	14	46.7	40	50.0
M	24	48.0	16	53.3	40	50.0
Total	50	100.0	30	100.0	80	100.0

Table 3: Biochemical Parameters of Study Participants

Variable	Diabetic (n=50)		Control (n=30)	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
FBG (mmol/L)	12.04	±0.71	4.61	±0.53
HbA1c (%)	8.44	±0.75	5.05	±0.42
Serum Calcium (mmol/L)	9.01	±0.48	9.08	±0.40
Serum Magnesium (mmol/L)	1.47	±0.34	1.89	±0.18

Table 4: Pearson correlation between serum electrolytes and glycemc indices in diabetic participants.

Variable	FBG (r)	p-value	HbA1c (r)	p-value
Serum Calcium	-0.050	0.662	-0.105	0.356
Serum Magnesium	-0.559	0.000	-0.622	0.000

Table 5: Comparison of Serum Electrolytes in Diabetic Participants with and without Complications

Variable	With Complications Mean ± SD	Without Complications Mean ± SD	t-value	p-value
Calcium (mmol/L)	9.006 ± 0.448	9.018 ± 0.508	-0.077	0.939
Magnesium (mmol/L)	1.563 ± 0.332	1.421 ± 0.333	1.407	0.166

Table 6: Anthropometric characteristics of diabetic and control participants

Parameter	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	p-value
Weight (kg)	Diabetic	50	64.20	10.50	1.49	-0.128	0.898
	Control	30	64.47	5.63	1.03		
Height (m)	Diabetic	50	1.680	0.028	0.004	-3.299	0.001*
	Control	30	1.704	0.034	0.006		
BMI (kg/m ²)	Diabetic	50	23.14	3.21	0.46	1.418	0.160
	Control	30	22.22	1.96	0.36		

p < 0.05 indicates statistical significance.

Discussion

This study investigated the regulation of serum calcium and magnesium in people with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM). It assessed their dependence on glycemic control, the presence of diabetes-related complications, and basic anthropometric parameters.

Socio-demographic data showed an older age distribution among participants with diabetes, which differed significantly from that of controls. The largest percentages of diabetic participants were in the 40–49, 50–59, and 60–69 age groups (30–32 per cent in each), whereas the percentage below 40 years was 8 per cent. Conversely, control participants under the age of 40 constituted 63.3 per cent. This observation is consistent with Mugisha, 2024's (2024) report that T2DM prevalence rises with age, caused by the gradual degradation of β -cells and insulin resistance. The gender ratio among the samples was balanced in both groups, and this is supported by ElSayed et al. (2023), who note that although biological sex can influence diabetes complications, prevalence rates in both men and women can be similar.

Analysis of biochemical variables demonstrated that diabetic participants exhibited significantly higher mean fasting blood glucose (FBG: 12.04 ± 0.71 mmol/L) and glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c: $8.44 \pm 0.75\%$) levels than controls (FBG: 4.61 ± 0.53 mmol/L; HbA1c: $5.05 \pm 0.4\%$). Serum magnesium levels were significantly lower in people with diabetes (1.47 ± 0.34 mmol/L) than in controls (1.89 ± 0.18 mmol/L), consistent with extensive evidence linking hypomagnesemia to insulin resistance, reduced insulin uptake, and oxidative stress, as presented by Radmanesh et al. (2023). Serum calcium showed no significant group difference and hence does not appear to be a helpful glycemic biomarker in this population.

The correlation analysis demonstrated a considerable negative association between serum magnesium and FBG ($r = -0.559$, $p < 0.001$) and HbA1c ($r = -0.622$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting an inverse association between magnesium levels and glycemic control. These results are consistent with previous studies, in which Kuppusamy et al. (2022) reported that magnesium is pivotal to insulin receptor function, carbohydrate metabolism, and glucose transfer. On the other hand, serum calcium showed no significant associations with glycemic indices, indicating no direct role in regulating glucose, as explained by Contreras-Ferrat et al. (2014).

The study found no significant differences in serum magnesium or calcium among people with diabetes with and those without reported complications associated with the disease, namely, neuropathy, nephropathy, or retinopathy. Although hypomagnesemia is frequently associated with an increased risk of microvascular and macrovascular complications, as reported by Gautam et al. (2024), the lack of a significant association in the present study could be due to the small study sample or the relatively short disease duration in some cases.

Anthropometric measurements revealed that body mass index (BMI) was higher in people with diabetes (23.14 – 23.21 kg/m²) than in controls (19.6 – 22.22 kg/m²), although the difference was not statistically significant. Patients with diabetes were significantly shorter ($p = 0.001$), whereas differences in weight were not statistically significant. While obesity is a known risk condition in T2DM development, as Ojuka and Goyaram (2014) noted, the BMI levels of both cohorts in this study were observed within the normal range, implying that additional factors related to metabolism or genes might be more prevalent determinants in this group, as highlighted by Itam et al. (2022).

In general, the results strongly indicate the potential value of magnesium as a biochemical indicator of glycemic control in T2DM, whereas serum calcium has little relevance in this regard.

Conclusion

T2DM patients in Osun State exhibit significantly lower serum magnesium levels than healthy controls, with strong negative correlations between magnesium and both FBG and HbA1c. Calcium levels showed no meaningful relationship with glycemic control or complications.

Novelty

The novelty of this study lies in a combined evaluation of calcium and magnesium, with a focus on glycemic control and complications. Rather than examining only glucose levels, this research links electrolyte imbalance with glycemic control (HbA1c levels) and Microvascular complications (neuropathy, nephropathy, retinopathy). This integrated approach strengthens the pathophysiological understanding of the potential biomarker exploration.

The study suggests that serum magnesium and calcium are predictive markers of poor glycemic control or risk of complications.

Limitations

- Serum Levels May Not Reflect Total Body Stores, especially for magnesium; intracellular magnesium is more accurate than serum levels.
- Confounding Variables may influence results. Factors such as: Renal functions, Medications, Dietary intake and Duration of diabetes.
- Single-Centre Study: Results may not be generalizable beyond the study population.
- Measurement Constraints: Total serum calcium may be affected by albumin levels unless corrected calcium is calculated.

Recommendations

1. **Clinical practice:** Incorporate routine serum magnesium assessment in T2DM management protocols.
2. **Nutrition education:** Encourage magnesium-rich diets and consider supplementation under medical supervision.
3. **Policy development:** National diabetes guidelines should integrate micronutrient monitoring to improve outcomes.
4. **Further research:** Larger longitudinal studies are needed to confirm causal links and evaluate the benefits of magnesium correction.

Future research

- Longitudinal Studies: Prospective cohort studies to determine whether magnesium or calcium imbalance predicts worsening glycemic control over time.
- Interventional Trials: Randomised controlled trials evaluating magnesium supplementation effects on HbA1c, Insulin resistance, and Diabetic complications.

References

- Adeleye, J. (2021). The hazardous terrain of Diabetes mellitus in Nigeria: The time for action is now. *Research Journal of Health Sciences*, 9(1), 69–76. <https://doi.org/10.4314/rejhs.v9i1.8>
- Adeloye, D., Ige, J. O., Aderemi, A. V., Adeleye, N., Amoo, E. O., Auta, A., & Oni, G. (2017). Estimating the prevalence, hospitalisation and mortality from type 2 diabetes mellitus in Nigeria: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMJ Open*, 7(5), e015424. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2016-015424>
- Ahn, C., Kang, H., Lee, J., Hong, E., Jung, E., Yoo, Y., & Jeung, E. (2018). Bisphenol A and octylphenol exacerbate type 1 diabetes mellitus by disrupting calcium homeostasis in the mouse pancreas. *Toxicology Letters*, 295, 162–172. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.toxlet.2018.06.1071>
- American Diabetes Association. (2023). *Standards of Medical Care in Diabetes*. Diabetes Care.
- Barbagallo, M., & Dominguez, L. J. (2015). Magnesium and type 2 diabetes. *World Journal of Diabetes*, 6(10), 1152–1157.

- Cho, N. H. (2018). IDF Diabetes Atlas: Global estimates of diabetes prevalence. *Diabetes Research and Clinical Practice*, 138, 271–281.
- Contreras-Ferrat, A., Lavandero, S., Jaimovich, E., & Klip, A. (2014). Calcium signalling in insulin action on striated muscle. *Cell Calcium*, 56(5), 390–396. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceca.2014.08.012>
- Dastgerdi, A. H., Rad, M. G., & Soltani, N. (2022). The therapeutic effects of magnesium on insulin secretion and insulin resistance. *Advanced Biomedical Research*, 11(1), 54. https://doi.org/10.4103/abr.abr_366_21
- Deol, N. R., & Bashir, N. D. S. (2024). Exploring the complications of type 2 diabetes mellitus: Pathophysiology and management strategies. *EPRA International Journal of Research & Development (IJRD)*, 173–182. <https://doi.org/10.36713/epra17838>
- Diabetes Mellitus. *MAEDICA – a Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 17(3). <https://doi.org/10.26574/maedica.2022.17.3.596>
- Divya, S., SMH, F. S., Chindhiha, S., Suganthi, M., Vincy, S. J., Chandrasekar, M., & Kandaswamy, D. S. (2021). HYPOMAGNEAEMIA AND HYPOCALCAEMIA THE MAJOR MISSED OUT CLINICAL CONDITION IN THE MANAGEMENT OF DIABETES. *International Journal of Clinical and Biomedical Research*, 16. <https://doi.org/10.31878/ijcbr.2021.72.04>
- ElSayed, N. A., Aleppo, G., Bannuru, R. R., Beverly, E. A., Bruemmer, D., Collins, B. S., Cusi, K., Darville, A., Das, S. R., Ekhlaspour, L., Fleming, T. K., Gaglia, J. L., Galindo, R. J., Gibbons, C. H., Giurini, J. M., Hassanein, M., Hilliard, M. E., Johnson, E. L., Khunti, K., ... Gabbay, R. A. (2023). Summary of Revisions: Standards of Care in Diabetes—2024. *Diabetes Care*, 47. <https://doi.org/10.2337/dc24-srev>
- Familoni, O., Odusan, O., Odewabi, A., Idowu, A., & Adekolade, A. (2017). Patterns and correlates of serum magnesium levels in subsets of type 2 diabetes mellitus patients in Nigeria. *Indian Journal of Endocrinology and Metabolism*, 21(3), 439. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijem.ijem_190_16
- Galicia-Garcia, U., Benito-Vicente, A., Jebari, S., Larrea-Sebal, A., Siddiqi, H., Uribe, K. B., Ostolaza, H., & Martín, C. (2020). Pathophysiology of Type 2 diabetes mellitus. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 21(17), 6275. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms21176275>
- Gautam, S., Mittal, C., Ranjan, A., & Singh, G. (2024). Association of Diabetic Peripheral Neuropathy with Micronutrients. *PubMed*, 72(5), 65–67. <https://doi.org/10.59556/japi.72.0493>
- Gröber, U. (2023). Magnesium – the metabolic Blockbuster. *Asian Journal of Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 11(2). <https://doi.org/10.53043/2347-3894.acam11009>
- Guerrero-Romero, F., & Rodríguez-Morán, M. (2002). Low serum magnesium levels and metabolic syndrome. *Archives of Medical Research*, 33(5), 512–520.
- Hamarshih, M., Hamshari, S., Nazzal, Z., Snobar, F., Mletat, R., Abu-Mazen, O., & Maraqa, B. (2022). Hypomagnesemia and poor glycemic control among type 2 diabetic patients: A cross-sectional study. *Indian Journal of Endocrinology and Metabolism*, 26(6), 575–580. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijem.ijem_213_22

- Hashim, Z. R., Qasim, Q. A., & ALabbood, M. H. (2022). The Association of Serum Calcium and Vitamin D with Insulin Resistance and Beta-Cell Dysfunction among People with Type 2 Diabetes. *PubMed*, 77(5), 1593–1600. <https://doi.org/10.22092/ari.2022.357641.2081>
- Hossain, M. J., Al-Mamun, M., & Islam, M. R. (2024). Diabetes mellitus, the fastest growing global public health concern: Early detection should be focused. *Health Science Reports*, 7(3). <https://doi.org/10.1002/hsr2.2004>
- Itam, A. H., Ogarekpe, Y. M., Edem, B., Agboola, A. R., Okpara, H. C., & Okokon, E. O. (2022). Association between Serum Calcium Concentration and Glycated Haemoglobin in Type II Diabetic Nigerian Patients. *BIOMED Natural and Applied Science*, 02(03), 25–32. <https://doi.org/10.53858/bnas02032532>
- Kebir, N. E., & Zahzeh, T. (2022). Magnesium Deficiency Associated with Stress, Systemic Inflammation, and Insulin Resistance in Diabetes Mellitus: A Review. *Egyptian Academic Journal of Biological Sciences. C: Physiology and Molecular Biology/Egyptian Academic Journal of Biological Sciences. C, Physiology and Molecular Biology*, 14(1), 31–46. <https://doi.org/10.21608/eajbsc.2022.213962>
- Kocyigit, E., Akturk, M., & Koksall, E. (2023). Relationships between serum and dietary magnesium, calcium, and metabolic parameters in women with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Clinical Nutrition ESPEN*, 54, 304–310. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clnesp.2023.01.035>
- Kostov, K. (2019). Effects of magnesium deficiency on mechanisms of insulin resistance in Type 2 diabetes: Focusing on the processes of insulin secretion and signaling. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 20(6), 1351. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms20061351>
- Kuppusamy, S., Dhanasinghu, R., Sakthivadivel, V., Kaliappan, A., Gaur, A., Balan, Y., Tadi, L. J., & Sundaramurthy, R. (2022). Association of Serum Magnesium with Insulin Indices in Patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. *MAEDICA – a Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 17(3), 596. <https://doi.org/10.26574/maedica.2022.17.3.596>
- Mugisha, E. K. (2024). The growing diabetes epidemic: a primary health concern for Nigeria's diverse population. *Research Invention Journal of Scientific and Experimental Sciences*, 4(2), 5–10. <https://doi.org/10.59298/rijses/2024/42510>
- Oghagbon, E. K. (2018). Metabolic and clinical significance of type 2 diabetes; implications for rising prevalence in Nigeria. *Journal of BioMedical Research and Clinical Practice*, 1(2), 108–117. <https://doi.org/10.46912/jbrcp.v1.i2.2018.55>
- Ojuka, E. O., & Goyaram, V. (2014). Increasing prevalence of Type 2 diabetes in Sub-Saharan Africa: not only a case of inadequate physical activity. *Medicine and Sport Science/Medicine and Sport*, 27–35. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000357333>
- Pham, P. C. (2007). Hypomagnesemia in patients with Type 2 DM. *Clinical Journal of the American Society of Nephrology*, 2(2), 366–373.
- Radmanesh, A., Choromzade, S., Akade, E., Bahadoram, M., & Kaydani, G. A. (2023). Magnesium deficiency as a contributing factor to type 2 diabetes: a review of the literature. *Journal of Renal Endocrinology*, 9, e25086. <https://doi.org/10.34172/jre.2023.25086>

- International Research Journal of Medical and Pharmaceutical Sciences Vol. 11(2)
- S, D., Smh, F. S., S, C., M, S., Vincy, S., M, C., & Kandaswamy, S. (2021). Hypomagnesaemia and Hypocalcaemia: The Major Missed Out Clinical Condition in The Management of Diabetes. *International Journal of Clinical and Biomedical Research*, 16–22. <https://doi.org/10.31878/ijcbr.2021.72.04>
- Sanjeevi, N., Freeland-Graves, J., Beretvas, S. N., & Sachdev, P. K. (2018). Trace Element Status in Type 2 Diabetes: A Meta-Analysis. *JOURNAL OF CLINICAL AND DIAGNOSTIC RESEARCH*. <https://doi.org/10.7860/jcdr/2018/35026.11541>
- Volpe, S. L. (2013). Magnesium in disease prevention. *Nutrition Reviews*, 71(2), 121–131.
- Weiser, A., Feige, J. N., & Marchi, U. D. (2021). Mitochondrial Calcium Signalling in Pancreatic β -Cell. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 22(5), 2515. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms22052515>